

Toychieva Nasibakhon Suranbaevna

Teacher of Samarkand State University,

Faculty of Philology, Interfaculty Department of Russian Language

MODERN USE OF TERMS FOR HOUSEHOLD SERVICES IN UZBEK AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

Annotation:In this article, one of the topical topics of the day is about daily household words used in everyday life in Russian and Uzbek languages. First, this article contains evidence of speech, and the main part of the article contains examples of actively used words in Uzbek and Russian.

Keywords:vocabulary and grammatical structure, active words, vocabulary, daily vocabulary, маяк, счёты, yogurt.

People communicate with each other through words throughout their lives. Speech is the use of language in the processes of expression and exchange of ideas, a certain way of life of language as a separate type of social activity. Speech refers to the processes of its oral (voice) and written manifestation, that is, the process of speaking and its result (speech ideas, words, stored in memory or recorded in writing).

Each person's speech is individual and has its own characteristics; However, the main elements of the language - vocabulary and grammatical structure do not belong only to individuals, but are universal, that is, they apply to a specific language community. Speech is closely related to a person's thinking, his consciousness. A person's thoughts are formed and exist in speech. Thanks to the speech and on the basis of the speech, it becomes possible to abstractly reflect the existence in a general way, to think logically and conceptually, leaving the sphere of individuality and becoming a product of the community. Speech is of great importance in the manifestation and action of other aspects of a person's psyche, his intuition, perception, memory, thoughts, feelings, will, etc., and in the development of a person's consciousness. Depending on the field of speech application, artistic speech, scientific speech, and official speech have forms. In any form and in any case, accuracy, fluency, simplicity, impressiveness should remain the most important features of speech.

There are active words in human point of view. The language has two layers of vocabulary - active and passive. Active vocabulary includes words that are often used by native speakers. Passive reserve consists of words that are rarely used in speech (obsolete words and neologisms). Obsolete words are words that have fallen out of active use. Daily vocabulary includes words that are actively used in the lexicon.

Daily vocabulary "a dictionary containing words of everyday use that name things and events in everyday life, that is, the general way of life, the environment around us, customs, morals, etc."¹

Daily vocabulary - a dictionary that contains words that name things and events that are common in the everyday life of all population groups. A large group of everyday vocabulary is very diverse and interesting in terms of origin and time of appearance, and includes clothes, shoes, kitchen utensils, food, buildings, animals, plants, human character, o consists of folk names of games, customs, ceremonies and agriculture.

¹ Гриценко П. Ю. Ареальне варіювання лексики. К.: Наукова думка, 1990. 272 с.

Daily vocabulary in Uzbek and Russian languages has always been relevant. A language cannot develop on its own. Also applies to other languages. In the last century, many words from the Russian language were introduced into the Uzbek language. For this reason, the excess or inappropriateness of Russian words is noticeable in Uzbek texts and communication. Similarly, some words were absorbed from Turkic (Uzbek language) into Russian. Below we give examples of some words that are actively used in Russian and Uzbek.

The word **mayak**, which is actively used in the Uzbek language, is actually a word borrowed from the Russian language.

Beacon is from the Russian word **маяк**. The word lighthouse is originally derived from the word *mayat* - to shake, to vibrate. Literally, it means one who sways in the distance. In Uzbek, it means a device in the form of a tower built on the coast or islands to guide ships. In the figurative sense, it is also used instead of the words "example" and "mashal":

Kema uchun mayoq, sayyoh uchun kompas, Yer uchun Quyosh aziz bo'lgani kabi...² (As a lighthouse is for a ship, a compass is for a traveler, and the Sun is dear to the Earth)

Chot, which was actively used in calculations in the recent past, is actually a word that came from the Russian language to the Uzbek language. Chot is from the Russian word **счёты**. Originally, *schyot* is derived from the noun "count" and "считать" - to count. This word, which means a calculation device, was transferred to Uzbek with sound changes. These devices are hardly used now. It is mostly used by children who are learning to count or add and subtract.

Buxgalteriya xonasidagi cho'tlarning shaq-shuqi, odamlarning uzuq-yuluq gaplari endi aniqroq eshitalardi.³ (The clatter of chatter in the accounting room and the chatter of people could now be heard more clearly.)

The Russian language also has words borrowed from the Turkic (Uzbek) language that are widely used in the current Russian language. For example, the word **yogurt**. In Mahmud Koshghari's work "Devonu Lugatit Turk" this word appears in **yo'g'rut** form, meaning yogurt. There are places where the word yogurt is used in the same sense. So, in ancient times, these two words were used synonymously.

Also, the word "Tovar" that is widely used in Russian is actually an Uzbek word. The Uzbek meaning of this word is product.

O'l aning birla tavar yarishdi – U sherigi bilan tovarni teng bo'lishdi.⁴

In conclusion, it can be said that the Uzbek and Russian languages have words that are actively used in everyday life. These words are often used in everyday life.

² From the newspaper.

³ From the newspaper.

⁴ Mahmud Koshg'ariy "Devonu lug'atit turk".

References:

1. Гриценко П. Ю. Ареальне варіювання лексики. К.: Наукова думка, 1990. 272 с.
2. Бытовая лексика: семантические и функциональные особенности (на материале прозы Юрия Вэлла).
3. Брагина Н. Г. Память в языке и культуре / Н. Г. Брагина. - М.: Языки славянских культур, 2007. - 526 с.
4. Mahmud Koshg'ariy "Devonu lug'atit turk".